

Impact of Utilization of E-Learning Technologies on Academic Performance of Undergraduate Business Education Students in Universities in Delta and Edo States

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ABSTRACT

The study examined impact of utilization of e-learning technologies on academic performance of undergraduate business education students in universities in Delta and Edo States. The aspects of e-learning technologies examined were: availability of e-learning technologies, utilization of e-learning technologies, impact of e-learning technologies, commitment to online activities and social media technologies and strategies for improving the utilization of e-learning technologies. Correspondingly, the moderating influence of gender, age, educational qualification in view and academic level were examined. Five research questions were raised and answered and five hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The survey research method was used for the study. The stratified random sampling technique was adopted and the sample size was 100 business education students. The instrument used for the study was a structured questionnaire and it was validated by three experts. The test-retest method was used to ascertain the reliability of the instrument and the PPMC reliability of 0.86 was obtained. Data collected were analyzed using Mean, Standard Deviation, t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The findings of the study revealed that e-learning technologies have a great impact on the academic performance of undergraduate business education students in universities in Delta and Edo States to a great extent. Also, that there was no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female business education students on the strategies for improving utilization of e-learning technologies in business education programmes in universities Delta and Edo States among others. It was concluded that utilization of e-learning technologies has great impact on academic performance of undergraduate business education students in universities in Delta and Edo State. Based on the findings, it was recommended that curriculum planners of the universities should make deliberate efforts to provide curriculum that will accommodate the utilization of e-learning software and technology, since the e-learning technologies enhance the academic performance of students.

INTRODUCTION:

Modern technology is one of the factors sharpening the global economy and producing rapid changes in contemporary society. This technology enabled instructional method to aim at improving the quality of education and student academic performance. The modern technology is a tool used to remove geographical barriers as it aids everybody to learn anytime and anywhere even without the presence of the lecturer. One of the technologies which have greatly influenced education is the Information and Communication Technology (ICT). The use of information and communication technology as a means of improving the efficiency and effectiveness in business education is not in doubt. With the introduction of information and communication technology (ICT), there have been changes in pedagogical delivery system.

Business education has been described as education for and about business (Okwuanaso & Nwazor, 2000; Nwosu, 2003). In other words, business education teaches knowledge and competencies required in business. According to Umoeshiet (2015), Business Education is an aspect of learning that prepares individuals for roles in business and offers them knowledge about business. Business education is considered as the pedagogical knowledge and business competencies necessary for teaching business attitude, concept, skills and knowledge. Business education is seen as a programme that has promoted skills which enable an individual to function effectively and efficiently, as an employee, or employer.

Akudolu (2012) believed that the advent of information communication technology has given rise to the formulation of new educational objectives which requires innovation and modification in the content, method and evaluation strategies.

Electronic Learning (EL) is an integral part of information and communication technology which its principle is connectivity, a process by which computers and electronic devices are networked to connect people to share information and knowledge for personal, academic or professional growth and development. E-learning has become an increasingly popular learning approach in higher educational institutions due to vast growth of internet technology and so it's expected to influence positively the academic performance of the business education students in universities in the globe especially in Nigeria.

Electronic learning (EL) is the use of Information and Communication Technology e.g. Internet, Computer, Mobile phone, Learning Management System (LMS), Televisions, Radios and others to enhance teaching and learning activities. E-learning is a unifying term used to describe the fields of online learning, web-based training and technology delivered instructions (Oye, Salleh, & Iahad, 2010). E-learning has become an increasingly popular learning approach in higher educational institutions due to vast growth of internet technology and so it's expected to influence positively the academic performance of the business education students in tertiary institutions in the globe especially in Universities in Nigeria. In the opinion of

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Oluwalola (2006) the internet is a global collection of many different types of computers, computer operators and computer networks that are linked together through telephone lines, satellites, microphones, and all other possible devices.

University education just like Business Education is concerned with the development and acquisition of skills and knowledge necessary for economic survival and development. University education and e-learning are interrelated. More also both lay emphasis on competency skill acquisition and knowledge that are required in the 21st century world of work. E-learning is widely used in many universities in the world today, but the researcher observed that there is rising dissatisfaction among employers of labour on the poor performance, lack of competencies and skills of business education graduates in the use of modern technologies in the new world of work. There were series of arguments that in some universities, their E-learning does not add any value to the teaching and learning activities of the institutions and that they do not investigate the impact of E-learning on students' academic performance, that much research has not been done on the new technologies and application software available for E-learning, that students commitment to online activities negatively affects the academic performance of undergraduates of Business education Students in universities in Delta and Edo States.

Okoro and Umoeshiet (2021), opined that e-learning is an essential structural tool that is required for effective and efficient instructional delivery for University programme in Nigerian Universities.

Most of the existing research reports in this regard are suggesting ways and means of addressing the problem of poor academic performance among business education students in universities and they appear rather to dwell more on teacher/government effectiveness factors rather than student/teacher factors and that is the gap this work has come to fill.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to investigate the impact of the utilization of e-learning technologies on academic performance of undergraduate business education students in universities in Delta and Edo States.

Research Questions

Specifically, the study will determine:

1. The extent to which the e-learning technologies are available for undergraduate students for business education programme in universities in Delta and Edo States?
2. The extent to which the E-learning technologies have impact on the academic performance of undergraduate Business Education Students in universities in Delta and Edo States?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of the Business Education students on the availability of E-learning technologies for undergraduate business education students' programme in universities in Delta and Edo States based on gender.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of Business Education students on the impact of utilization of e-learning technologies on the academic performance of undergraduate business education students in universities in Delta and Edo States based on qualification in view.

The scope of the study covers “the impact of the utilization of E-learning technologies on the academic performance of undergraduate business education students in Universities” and it is delimited to Delta and Edo States.

Rosenshine’s Learning Theory

Barak Rosenshine is an educational psychologist who propounded a theory of learning in 1982, with ten (10) guiding principles, which in summary emphasizes the importance of giving students sufficient time to practice retrieval, ask questions, and get the desired help. The students must not stop after learning the information once, they must continue to rehearse it by summarizing, analysing or applying their knowledge.

On the theoretical framework about e-learning the authors/psychologists believed that the work in constructivism and student involvement provided the bedrock. In the theories of Seymour Papert 1980 and Rosenshine 1982, they emphasized on E-learner-centred and skill acquisition and development. These theories argue that for a particular curriculum to achieve the effects intended, it must illicit sufficient student effort and investment of energy to bring about the desired learning and development .

Historical Overview of E-learning

E-learning was developed in 1960s at the tertiary institution of Illinois. Where students were made to have access to recorded lecture resources via the computers terminal that have link with television or audio device. Later in the year two psychology Professors Patrick, Suppose and Richard C. Atkinson of Tertiary institution of Stanford carried out an experiment. They used the computer to teach young children, reading and mathematics in elementary school in East Palo Alto in California.

In 1963, the first computer for instruction was installed by Bernard Luskin in a community college, which has connection with Stanford Tertiary institution. As at 1970 Luskin took an appointment with Kand Corporation where he engaged in analysing obstacles to computer assisted instructions. This development provided opportunity for distance learning courses using the computer in some educational institutions.

Further developments in e-learning include computer based learning, which was developed by Murray Turoff and Starr Roxanne Hilz in 1970 at the New Jersey Institute of Technology and at Tertiary institution of Guelph in Canada. By 1980 it was recorded that access to course contents became possible in college Libraries. Cassandra B. Whyte played a great role on e-learning in higher education; the advent of collaborative learning gave rise to open part of Europe and America. 1990 saw the advent of World Wide Web, (www).

E-learning as a Concept

E-Learning simply means electronic learning. It is an aspect of information and communication technology which can be described as an innovative means of impacting knowledge electronically. According to Obikaeze and Onyechi (2011) defined e-learning as forms and non-formal education that uses electronic delivery method such as internet based learning delivery packages, CD-Rom, online video conferencing, website or e-mail to manage the relationship between teachers and learners. E-learning involves certain skills and knowledge. E-learning is also seen as the acquisition of knowledge and skills using electronic technology such as computers and the internet based software and local and wide area networks. In the same vain Azih and Nwosu (2011) agree that e-learning is a pertinent tool for effective teaching and learning. E-learning is commonly associated with higher education and corporate

training, e-learning encompasses learning at all levels both formal and non-formal education that has an information network – the internet, and intranet (LAN) or extranet (WAN), whether wholly or in part for course delivery, interaction and/or facilitation of online learning.

The views of Okoli and Ifeakor (2011) stated that e-learning is essentially the computer and network that enable the transfer of skills and knowledge. They further asserted that the use of electronic applications and processes to learn include web based learning, computer based learning, virtual classrooms and digital collaborations, content is delivered via the internet/extranet, audio or video tape.

In his contribution, Azih (2003) further described e-learning as a kind of learning that is possible using the computer. This learning on the computer simply means online knowledge acquisition through CD-Rom. He also emphasized that online teaching and learning method needs the use of browsers such as internet explorer or Netscape navigator. The e-learning facilities can be in the form of audio, visual and audio/visual.

This was reaffirmed by Ong and Lai (2006) saying that e-learning is instruction delivered via all electronic media including the internet, intranet, extranet, satellite broadcast, audio/video tape, interactive television and CD-Rom. While Back, Jung and Kim believed that e-learning should be understood in a wide sense, including the use of electronic means of teaching and learning in classrooms. Face to face and outside – a distance, both individually or in a collaborative way as well as in a blended format of classroom and distance studies. They maintained that e-learning is not an end itself but rather a wide concept which can be used for various forms of teaching and learning ranging from formal education to informal learning. In their opinion, it may start with audio-visual tools used in the classrooms and go far as interactive internet based collaboration of students and teacher. Finally, Onowor (2011) summarized that e-learning comprises:

- All forms of electronically supported learning and teaching
- The use of technology to enable people to learn anytime and anywhere.
- The use of information communication technology (ICT) in developing skills as well as concepts based knowledge.
- The use of instructional media in form of texts image, animation video and audio devices
- Computer and network to enabled the transfer of skills and knowledge.

tance teaching), but also in various teaching philosophies (for instance behaviourism or constructivism).

Benefits of Utilization of E-Learning Technologies in University Education Programme

There are a lot of benefits in the utilization of e-learning technologies in university education programme. Lhi (1997) in Nwosu (2017) identified the following as benefits of e-learning.

1. **Convenience and portability:** E-Learning accords the student the advantage of learning anywhere and anytime. It does not mostly require fixed class rooms where the student attends daily as it also allows students to fix and listen to lectures anytime more so, learning materials can be carried about and lectures administered even on the move. This allows student's easier understanding since the pace is determined exclusively by the student and pressure is dissipated on the student to scheme of work.
2. **Cost and Selection:** The student can choose from a wide range of courses to meet need. It offers degree, vocational and certificate programmes provides continuing education, provide individuals courses for selection, wide range of prices are set to fit the students budget.

3. **Flexibility:** E-learning accommodates learner's preference and needs. It is mainly student centred. One can study through chosen instructors or self-study. There is opportunity to slipover materials /topics that one already know and focus on those one would like to know and use the tool best suitable to the student for learning.
4. **Higher Retention:** E-learning or online learning will draw the students' attention to topics of internet. Studies show that because of this and the variety of delivery method used to reach different types of learners. Retention is frequently better than in traditional classroom.
5. **Greater Collaboration:** Technology tools make collaboration among students much easier since many projects involve collaborative learning. The online environment is easier and often more comfortable to work in since learners do not have meet face to face.
6. **Global opportunities:** Global learning communities are at the student's finger tips with online learning. The e-learning technology used, gives on-line instructional designers the ability to build in tools that take you to resources that may not be seen in a traditional classroom.
7. **Improved Performance:** Lhi (1997) in Nwosu (2017) also revealed that researchers have shown that students in online learning generally perform better than those in normal classroom. According to a 12 years research conducted by the US department of education, there is a massive influx of students into online education, a greater percent.
8. **Increased access to instructor of the highest quality.** E-learning offers students opportunity to have access to instructors of the highest calibre who can share their knowledge with students, allowing students to attend courses across physical political and economic boundaries. It also allows student's access to their fellow students who will share their experiences and solutions as well as allow greater communication among students across different geographical zones making studying wonderful.
9. **Cost Reduction:** There is a generally reduced expense since cost of daily transportation is eliminated.
10. **Skill Development:** To develop the skills and competencies needed in the 21st century and enable learners cope with new trends in their chosen profession and career. E-learning transforms and develops students to meet the present requirements of graduates needed to undertake specific tasks at different areas, sectors, offices in global market. Bates (2009), states that a major argument for e-learning is that it enables learners to develop essential skills for knowledge based workers by embedding the use of information and communication technology within the curriculum.

Constraints to Utilization of E-learning Technologies in University Education Programme

There are a lot of constraints militating against the effective utilization of e-learning technologies in University education programme at the tertiary level. Muilenburg and Berge (2001) in Ezeugbor and Nwachukwu (2011) identified the following as constraint or challenges of e-learning implementation in Nigerian higher institutions.

1. **Unwillingness to adopt new technological innovation:** Getting a new idea adopted even when it has advantages is difficult. Accordingly innovation such as e-learning system, in higher education requires faculty to change their ways of teaching, such change does not come easily. However reluctance is major on the part of teacher's factor hindering the use of e-learning in Nigerian higher institutions.
2. **Lack of awareness of the effectiveness of e-learning:** Generally, there is still lack of awareness amongst the population (educators and students) especially parents about the effectiveness of e-learning. Many still feel the traditional learning mode is better.

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3. **Bandwidth use and connectivity:** Engaging content requires a rich combination of multimedia and connectivity limitations downloading of engaging content to the learners will be slow. This creates frustration and boredom among learners and affects the ease of learning.
4. **Lack of computer literacy:** In Nigeria, there is a large segment of the population that is computer illiterate. This is especially true in rural areas. This hinders the introduction and implementation of e-learning.
5. **Lack of technically experienced lecturers:** Most of the lecturers in Nigerian universities do not have competence in the use of e-learning in their institutions. Majority of lecturers who had taken leading jobs were taught without ICTs (e-learning) and they have not developed competence in the use of ICTs (e-learning), thus they cannot model good use of technology (Idowu, Adagunod & Popoola, 2003).
6. **Limited (e-learning) facilities:** Limited fund available to higher institutions have hindered the provision if needed facilities and infrastructure to promote e-learning usage. Most facilities of education and schools of education in Nigeria do not have dedicated laboratory for e-learning training. Classroom for e-learning are equally not equipped for usage. Thus, educators and trainee educators do not have access to e-learning technologies within their schools. The few available ones are well used mostly for administrative purposes.
7. **Inadequate course content for e-learning:** The curriculum for teacher education is centralized based on NUC draft benchmark and academic minimum standard. The content and strategy are based on single course model. It is meant to teach trainee teachers about how to learn or teach through the computer. While this is good for introductory stage its outcomes are very limited. They cannot furnish educators with the needed skills and knowledge of e-learning usage in their institution.
8. **Problem of electricity:** E-learning equipment are electrical equipment that requires electricity for operation. Most rural areas of Nigeria do not have electricity facility and in urban area electricity supply is epileptic, and this reduces the life span of hardware also militates against effective usage, even enthusiastic educators and students who have access to computer may be debarred from using them as a result of power outage.

Review of Empirical Studies

Yuning, Saxin and Cheng (2022) conducted a research on effect of e-learning on academic performance of undergraduate students at Nankai University, China. The study have hypothesis which were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The purpose of the study was to examine the effect of e-learning on the academic performance of undergraduate students at Nankai University in china. The descriptive survey research was used for the study. The purposive sampling technique was adopted and sample size was 361 students. The questionnaire was used in obtaining data. The descriptive and inferential statistics of mean, standard deviation and t-test were used to analyze the data. The findings of the study revealed that e-learning is positively and significance related to academic performance. E-learning enhance accessibility to effective learning and therefore boosts the performance of learners. The study also found that students can interact anytime and from anywhere with various educational material like messages, audio, picture video and more via the internet. The study also found that e-learning is positively and significance related to academic performance. Both studies are related in both the dependent and independent variables of the studies. The reviewed study used the purposive sampling technique while the current study used the simple random sampling technique. They differ in terms of geographical scope. The reviewed study was done in China while the current study was done in Nigeria.

Cai-Yu, Yuan-Yuan and Shih-Chih (2021). Carried out an investigation on the empirical study of college students' e-learning effectiveness and its antecedents towards the COVID-19 epidemic environment. Fourteen alternate hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The purpose of the study was to determine the effectiveness of e-learning and its antecedents towards the covid-19 epidemic environment on college students. The research design adopted for the study was the survey design. The population of the study was the entire medical students from first-to the fifth-year undergraduate students. The stratified sampling technique was adopted for the study and the sample size was 519 students. The multi-group analysis was used in analysing the data. The findings of the study revealed that college students' e-learning self-efficacy has a significant positive influence on e-learning effectiveness through e-learning strategies. Also, the study found that e-learning monitoring has a significant influence on e-learning strategies and offers indirect influence on e-learning effectiveness through e-learning strategies. Also, that e-learning attitude has a significant positive impact on e-learning motivations, and e-learning effectiveness is positively affected by e-learning attitude through e-learning motivations and e-learning strategies. The reviewed study is related to the current study in terms of the independent variable. The studies differ in terms of the dependent variable, population and geographical location. The reviewed study used medical students while the current study used business education students. The reviewed study was done in Taiwan while the current study was done in Nigeria.

Ejubovic and Puska (2019) examined impact of self-regulated learning on academic performance and satisfaction of students in the online environment. Two main hypotheses and ten alternate hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The purpose of the study was to determine the impact of self-regulated learning on academic performance and satisfaction of students in online environment. The survey research design was adopted and the population was students of 46 higher education institutions in B &H which were public and private universities. The simple random sampling technique was applied and the sample size was 1651 students. The questionnaire was used to obtain data for the study. The data collected were analyzed using the multiple regression analysis and the correlational analysis. The findings revealed that self-regulated learning influenced satisfaction and academic performance. Also, that environment structuring has a positive and significant influence on academic performance. The reviewed study is related to the current study in terms of the dependent variable. They both have hypotheses. Both studies differ in terms of the independent variables, geographical location. Also, the current study has research questions while the reviewed study does not have. The current study was done in Nigeria while the reviewed study was carried out in Germany.

Balakamakshi, and Savithri, (2021) investigated the effect of e-learning on students' academic performance at college level. Two null and two alternate hypotheses was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The purpose of the study was to determine the impact of e-learning on students' academic performance. It was a survey design study. The convenient sampling technique was adopted for the study. The sample size was 250 female students from colleges in Chennai. A 3-point rating scale was used in collecting data with the use of structured questionnaire. The collected data was analysed with the use of SPSS to obtain the percentage analysis and chi square. The findings of the study reviewed that e-learning enhances the quality of teaching and learning process. The study also showed that there was significant association between age and academic performance of students. Also that the association between flexible time and academic performance is highly significant. The reviewed study is related to the current study in terms of the independent and dependent

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variables. Both studies have hypotheses. Also, both studies have moderating variables. The reviewed study considered age and flexible time while the current study considered gender, age, educational qualification in view and academic level. They differ in terms of geographical location. The reviewed study used 3-point rating scale of Agreed, Neutral and Disagreed while the current study used 4-point rating scale of Very Great Extent, Great Extent, Little Extent and Very Little Extent with 4, 3, 2, and 1 point respectively. The current study used both male and female students but the reviewed study only made use of female students.

Elena, Svetlana, Natalia, and Yana (2021) carried out a study on Education policy: The Impact of E-Learning on Academic Performance. The purpose of the study was to determine the effect of e-learning on academic achievement and the magnitude of its impact on academic achievement. The research design adopted was the meta-analysis. Data were collected from 150 authors' observational studies carried out in Russia. The surveys of distant and partly-distant students were used to collect data. While the Cohen Model was used in analysing the result. The findings of the study revealed that e-learning has a significant beneficial impact on the academic success of students. Also, those sufficient ICT facilities can contribute to better learning and students' academic performance. The study is related to the current study in terms of the independent variables. Both studies differ in terms of the research method. The reviewed study is a meta-analytical study while the current study is a descriptive survey study. Both studies also differ in terms of geographical location. The reviewed study was conducted in Russia while the current study was done in Nigeria.

Okoli (2012) examined assessment of strategies for optimizing ICT usage among undergraduate Students. The study was a decipher survey which was carried out with undergraduates in two universities and a college of education. Purposive sample of 35 undergraduates were drawn from Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Kwara State University, Ilorin and Nsugbe College of Education. 35 copies of structured questionnaires were distributed out of which 25 copies were returned and all were found usable. The findings of the study showed that when these ICT facilities are made available and maintained, the undergraduates will develop courses online to be accessed by teachers and student, using video conferencing for groups outside the institutions, it also revealed that students use the PC's in discussion in class and outside classroom using internet, chatting, mentoring and use of CD-Rom instead of printing materials will be facilitated. Another finding is that all the administrative and instructional related strategies were perceived as necessary but the strategy of making a policy on compulsory possession of private computers by students on admission and the use of video conferencing were least rated. Both studies are related as they both examined the usage of ICTs (computer and e-learning technologies) in the teaching and learning of Tertiary education programme in Nigerian tertiary institution and further to determine the impact on academic performance of undergraduates of business education students in universities in Delta and Edo States precisely. The study differ in terms of geographical location.

Ezenwafor (2012), investigated adequacy of exposure to information and communication technology in business. The study sought to ascertain the adequacy of exposure received by graduating university education students and tertiary institutions in manipulating and utilizing various ICT equipment and software resources. The study is a descriptive survey which was carried out in Anambra State in four tertiary institutions. Two universities and two colleges of education, 418 graduating tertiary education students were used in the study. A structured

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questionnaire was used, the findings showed that the respondents were not very adequately exposed in utilizing any of the ICT (e-learning) software resources. The study however showed that, business educator in south-east universities possesses internet skills to great extent, this help in exposing their students in utilizing the resources. In addition to this is a revelation that respondent's exposure in manipulating ICT equipment and tools is inadequate. The study is related to the present study which is on utilization of e-learning in universities and tertiary institutions. The studies differ in terms of the geographical location. The reviewed study was done in Anambra State while the current study was done in Delta and Edo States.

Azih and Nwosu (2012) carried out a study to ascertain the extent of availability and utilization of e-learning facilities in tertiary institutions offering business courses in Ebonyi state. The population was all the undergraduates in the three tertiary institutions in Ebonyi State, comprising 8 lecturers from Ebonyi State Tertiary institution, 12 lecturers from Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic and 11 lecturers from Ebonyi State College of Education Ikwo. Out of the 31 copies of the questionnaire 30 copies were returned. The questionnaire had 46 Items which were used in the study. The findings revealed that the tertiary institutions do not have the necessary E-learning facilities needed for teaching and learning Tertiary education. The study also revealed non utilization of e-learning facilities and identified high cost of procurement and installation of e-learning centre, poor maintenance of existing communication and poor power supply as some challenges found to inhibit the availability and utilization of e-learning in tertiary institution in Ebonyi State. The reviewed study is related to the current study in terms of the independent variable. Both studies differ in terms of population, the reviewed study used university in one state while the current study used universities in two states. They also differ in terms of location. The reviewed study was done in Ebonyi State while the current state was done in Delta and Edo States.

Galy, Downey and Johnson (2011) conducted a study on the effect of using e-learning tools in online and campus-based classrooms on students' performance. Two hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The purpose of the study was to examine the effect of using e-learning tools in online ad campus-based classroom on students' performance. The survey research design was adopted. The population of the study comprised of students pursuing a Bachelors of business Administration, who were given the choice of enrolling in either online section or campus-based section of the same course during the Fall semester of 2009. The moderating variables of gender, age and city of residence was used in the study. The sampling technique adopted was purposive sampling and the sample size was students in Information Systems in organizations (IS), Human Resource Management (HRM), and I International Management (INTL). The questionnaire was used as a means for data collection. Method of data analysis was mean, standard deviation, t-test, correlation and regression analysis. Findings of the study revealed that e-learning tools as well as work, do play an important role in performance in both online and campus-based courses. Also, that there is a statistically significant number of students who do not believe that online courses are equal in value compared to those delivered on campus. Also, there was no significant difference between the final grades of the online and campus-based students. The reviewed study is related to the current study in terms of the independent and dependent variables. They both have hypotheses and moderating variables. They differ in terms of geographical scope. The reviewed study was carried out in USA while the current study was done in Nigeria.

Umoru and Zakka (2019) conducted a study on interactive technology competencies required by teachers of office technology and management for improved secretarial outcomes in

polytechnics in North-Central Nigeria. The study have hypotheses. The purpose of the study was to investigate the interactive technology competencies required by teachers of office technology and management for improved secretarial outcome in polytechnics in North-Central Nigeria. The study revealed the following as interactive technology competencies required by Teachers of Office Technology and Management to improve secretarial performance in polytechnics in North-Central Nigeria; ability to use interactive white boards, electronic board for teaching, ability to use interactive forms on the web to create feedback or ask questions, ability to organize video conferencing or internet phone chat (Skype, Team Speak), ability to use interactive on-line survey tools (Survey Monkey, Zoomerang), ability to use student response systems (clickers, wireless learning calculator systems, etc.), ability to use instant messaging/chat room for content delivery, ability to use interactive multimedia and presentation application for teaching, ability to use simulations, or virtual worlds (Ayiti, Elemental, Second Life, Civilization), ability to use interactive collaborative editing software (Wikis, Google Docs), ability to use online student video projects (using YouTube, Google Video), ability to use Web 2.0 tools to interact and collaborate for teaching and learning purposes, ability to use interactive E-book, ability to use educational cloud services to store, manage and process data, ability to use audience response pads, ability to create online interactive audio and video instructions. The reviewed study is related to the present study in terms of the e-learning technologies. Both studies differ in terms of the geographical scope. The reviewed study was carried out in North-Central Nigeria while the current study was done in Delta and Edo States in South-South Nigeria.

Methodology

The survey research method was used for the study. The stratified random sampling technique was adopted and the sample size was 100 business education students from the selected Universities in Delta and Edo States. The instrument was a self-developed questionnaire titled, "Impact of E-learning technologies Questionnaire (IUELQ)". Which was divided into two parts namely (Section A and Section B) Section A contained the demographic variables of the respondents, while Section B dealt with the research questions. The items in the Section B of the questionnaire was rated with a 4-point rating scale of Very Great Extent (**VGE**), Great Extent (**GE**), Little Extent (**LE**), and Very Little Extent (**VLE**), which was weighed 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. (See Appendix C, p. 84)

The instrument was face and content validated by the research supervisor, one expert from the Department of Business Education and one expert from the Department of Measurement and Evaluation all from Delta State University, Abraka.

Data collected was analysed with the use of mean, standard deviation, t-test, and One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used for testing the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Any mean that is less than 2.50 means little extent of utilization of e-learning technologies while any mean that is 2.50 -3.49 means Great Extent of utilization of e-learning technologies, while any mean at 3.50 and above means Very Great Extent of utilization of e-learning technologies.

Results:

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation responses on availability of e-learning technologies for undergraduate business education students

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S/N	To what extent are the following E – Learning Software Technologies available for teaching and learning business Education courses in your institution?	X	SD	REMARK
1.	Word Processing Software	3.31	0.83	GE
2.	Typing Software (Marvis Beacon, Ultrakey)	2.89	0.85	GE
3.	Data Base Software	2.62	0.95	GE
4.	Design and Graphic Software	2.62	1.07	GE
5.	Desktop Publishing Software	2.62	0.98	GE
6.	Internet Browsing Software	2.71	0.95	GE
7.	Statistical Analysis and Forecasting Software	2.52	0.96	GE
8.	E-mail Facilities	2.63	1.04	GE
9.	Interactive Websites	2.65	1.07	GE
10.	Intranet/Extranet	2.49	0.93	LE
11.	Online Tutorial in Zoom	2.45	1.01	LE
12.	Power point for Lecture Presentation	2.55	1.00	GE
13.	Spread Sheet (Excel) Software	2.85	1.07	GE
14.	Search Engine (eg. google.com firefox.com etc.)	2.57	1.03	GE
15.	Chat rooms (Facebook, Youtube, twitter and 2go)	2.68	1.11	GE
	GRAND MEAN/SD	2.68	0.99	GE

Data presented in Table 1 revealed that the mean responses of respondents on availability of e-learning technologies for undergraduate business education students ranged from 2.45 to 3.31, while the standard deviation ranged from 0.83 to 1.11. Similarly, the grand mean of 2.68 depicted that availability of e-learning technologies for undergraduate business education students in in universities in Delta and Edo States was to a Great extent. Also, the standard deviation showed that the respondents were not far apart in their responses. Although, Table 1 showed that the availability of intranet/extranet and online tutorial in zoom for undergraduate business education students was to a little extent. Which implied that these technologies were rarely available for use by the students.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation responses on impact of e-learning technologies on academic performance of undergraduate business education students

S/N	To what extent does the following E-learning software technologies has positive impact on the academic performance of undergraduate business Education students	X	SD	REMARK
1.	Word Processing Software	3.29	0.98	GE
2.	Typing Software (Marvis Beacon, Ultrakey)	2.85	0.77	GE
3.	Data Base Software	2.73	0.99	GE
4.	Internet Browsing Software	2.47	1.06	LE
5.	E-Electronic Books Software	2.66	0.92	GE

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6.	Statistical Analysis and Forecasting Software	2.56	1.08	GE
7.	E-mail Facilities	2.58	1.04	GE
8.	Motion Films	2.53	1.06	GE
9.	Interactive Websites	2.62	1.01	GE
10.	Intranet/Extranet	2.33	1.01	LE
11.	Online Tutorials in CD and DVD	2.58	1.06	GE
12.	Power point for Lecture Presentation Software	2.53	1.04	GE
13.	Spread Sheet (Excel) Software	2.63	1.02	GE
14.	Search Engine (eg. google.com firebox.com)	2.72	0.99	GE
15.	Chat rooms (Facebook, Youtube, twitter 2go)	2.70	0.99	GE
	GRAND MEAN/SD	2.65	1.00	GE

Data presented in Table 2 revealed that the mean responses of respondents on impact of e-learning technologies on academic performance of undergraduate business education students ranged from 2.33 to 3.29, while the standard deviation ranged from 0.77 to 1.06. Similarly, the grand mean of 2.65 depicts that impact of e-learning technologies on academic performance of undergraduate business education students in universities in Delta and Edo States was to a Great extent. Also, the standard deviation showed that the respondents were not far apart in their responses. Although, Table 3 showed that impact of e-learning technologies on academic performance of undergraduate business education students with regards to Internet Browsing Software and Intranet/Extranet was to a little extent.

For the hypotheses, any calculated p-value that is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected and any calculated p-value that was greater than 0.05 the null hypotheses was retained.

Table 3: t-test Analysis of Business Education students' Mean Ratings on the availability of E-learning technologies for undergraduate business education students' programme in universities in Delta and Edo States based on gender.

Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	α	p-value	Decision
Male	37	3.22	0.92				
Female	63	3.37	0.77	98	0.05	0.39	NS

Data presented in Table 3 indicates that the p-value on the availability of E-learning technologies for undergraduate business education students' programme is 0.39. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of business education students on the availability of E-learning technologies for undergraduate business education students' programme in universities in Delta and Edo States based on gender.

Table 4: t-test Analysis of Business Education students' Mean Ratings on the impact of utilization of e-learning technologies on the academic performance of undergraduate business education students in universities in Delta and Edo States based on qualification in view.

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Qualification	N	Mean	SD	df	α	p-value	Decision
B.Sc (Ed.)	59	3.31	1.02				
B.Ed.	41	3.27	0.92	98	0.05	0.85	NS

Data presented in Table 4 indicated that the p-value on the impact of utilization of e-learning technologies on the academic performance of undergraduate business education students in universities is 0.85. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of business education students on the impact of utilization of e-learning technologies on the academic performance of undergraduate business education students in universities in Delta and Edo States based on qualification in view.

Discussion of Findings

The study found in research question one that the following e-learning technologies are available for undergraduate business education students in universities in Delta and Edo States to a great extent. These e-learning technologies include Word Processing Software, Typing Software (Marvis Beacon, Ultrakey), Data Base Software, Design and Graphic Software, Desktop Publishing Software, Internet Browsing Software, Statistical Analysis and Forecasting Software. Others include E-mail Facilities, Interactive Websites, Power point for Lecture Presentation, Spread Sheet (Excel) Software, Search Engine (eg. google.com firefox.com etc.), and Chat rooms (Facebook, Youtube, twitter and 2go). This finding corroborate the findings of Yuning, et al. (2022) who found that students can interact anytime and from anywhere with various educational material like messages, audio, picture video and more via the internet. It contradicts the findings of Azih and Nwosu (2012) who discovered in their study that tertiary institutions do not have the necessary E-learning facilities needed for teaching and learning Tertiary education. However, it was observed from the results of data analysis that intranet/extranet and online tutorial in zoom for undergraduate business education students was barely available for the students use. These findings collaborate Elena, et al. (2021) who found that sufficient ICT facilities can contribute to better learning and students' academic performance.

The result of data analysis for research question three indicted that E-learning technologies have great impact on the academic performance of undergraduate Business Education Students in universities in Delta and Edo States. E-learning technologies have impact on the academic performance of undergraduate Business Education Students in universities in Delta and Edo States. The e-learning technologies that have great impact on academic performance of undergraduate business education students are, Word Processing Software, Typing Software (Marvis Beacon, Ultrakey), Data Base Software, E-Electronic Books Software, Statistical Analysis and Forecasting Software, E-mail Facilities, Motion Films, Online Tutorials in CD and DVD, Power point for Lecture Presentation Software, Spread Sheet (Excel) Software, Search Engine (eg. google.com firefox.com) and Chat rooms (Facebook, Youtube, twitter 2go).

The findings of the present study agreed with that of Galy, et al. (2011) that e-learning tools as well as work, do play an important role in performance in both online and campus-based courses. Also, it agreed with Yuning, et al. (2022) who found that e-learning is positively and significance related to academic performance. These findings corroborate with Elena, et al. (2021) who discovered that e-learning has a significant beneficial impact on the academic success of students. The findings of Ejubovic and Puska (2019) also support the findings of the present study that self-regulated learning influenced satisfaction and academic performance.

The findings of the present study collaborates Yousef, and Basem, (2020) who uphold in their study that, the implementation of e-learning strategy has a positive impact and statistically significant differences on the students' GPA.

Conclusion.

The main purpose of the study was to investigate the impact of the utilization of e-learning technologies on academic performance of undergraduate business education students in universities in Delta and Edo States. The content variables covered in this study include: E-learning technologies, software and academic performance.

The theoretical framework of the study was based on Constructivism Learning Theory propounded by Seymour Papert in 1980.

The findings of the study revealed that e-learning technologies have a great impact on the academic performance of undergraduate business education students in universities in Delta and Edo States to a great extent. Also, there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of the Business Education students on the availability of E-learning technologies for undergraduate business education **students' programme in universities in Delta and Edo States based on gender**, gender, age, educational qualification in view and academic level.

Recommendations:

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The management of university administration should ensure that the institution should make available intranet/extranet and also make provision for online tutorial in zoom for undergraduate business education students.
2. The lecturers should ensure that students make use of Desktop Publishing Software, Chat rooms (Facebook, Youtube, twitter 2go), Interactive Websites, Intranet/Extranet, and Online Tutorials in CD and DVD as they will enhance their academic performance.
3. Curriculum planners of the universities should make deliberate efforts to provide curriculum that will accommodate the utilization of e-learning software and technology, since the e-learning technologies enhance the academic performance of students.

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